

The escape room and breakout as an aid to learning STEM contents in primary schools: an examination of the development of pre-service teachers in Spain

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Abstract

Gamification consists of using game elements in non-game contexts, such as in education, aiming to promote cooperation, motivation, or engagement. Here, the Escape Room and Breakout games are in early stages in formal educational environments. Specifically, in primary education, this type of tools can be useful to support the teaching and learning process of pupils. This study aims to describe a BrEscapeRm (Escape Room and Breakout combine) used as educational tool to teach STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) contents in a science course of degree in Primary Education. After completing the activity, students' perception about the BrEscapeRm were gauged, resulting that they found it funny, interesting, motivating, and exciting. However, a certain rejection to the tasks containing calculation and science contents was detected. During BrEscapeRm development, students were very focused on each task and there was a sense of pleasure at the end of BrEscapeRm. Therefore, this activity could have multiple benefits for the student's motivation and engagement in learning in primary education.

Keywords

primary education; active learning; game-based learning; STEM education; pre-service teachers

Introduction

In recent years, active learning has become a significant movement in colleges and universities around the world, especially in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) courses (Chang and Hwang 2018; Mintzes and Walter 2020). Active learning consists of learning beyond the traditionally one-way transmission of knowledge in lecture-style classes (passive learning). This type of learning is a learner-centred teaching strategy, and it requires the students' participation in activities such as writing, discussion, oral presentation, and externalisation of cognitive processes in activities to achieve a meaningful learning (Prince 2004; Mizokami 2018). Although active learning is a learner-centred methodology, the instructor's role must be very active and being constantly attentive to the problems that may arise for the students in the classroom during the learning process (Prince 2004; Akınoğlu and Tandoğan 2007). At the same time, Freeman et al. (2014) also suggested that the learning environment is important to promote the students' participation in active learning context, since the student's engagement is crucial to achieve a quality learning while involved actively in teaching/learning activities (Symaco and Tee 2019).

Several studies show that active learning has multiple benefits such as the improvement of the students' performance, interpersonal and social skills, and learning how to learn (Smith et al. 2009; Hwang et al. 2018; Mizokami 2018). In fact, various studies (Aydoğan, Bozkurt, and Coskun

2015; Haak et al. 2011) analyse the active learning effects in students' performance and academic grades. However, there are other important advantages that can contribute to academic success such as the motivation, critical thinking, teamwork, or a better understanding of some concepts (Tsui 2002; González-Gómez, Jeong, and Cañada-Cañada 2019; Riivari, Kivijärvi, and Lämsä 2021). In addition to the importance of the cognitive domain, the influence of the affective domain on the teaching and learning process is noteworthy (González-Gómez, Jeong, and Gallego-Picó 2018; Yllana-Prieto, Jeong, and González-Gómez 2021a). Specifically, the effect of this affective component is even more influential in primary school. Pupils at this stage of schooling are more dependent on the emotional factor because they are at earlier stages of development. Therefore, it is essential to promote positive affectivity in STEM content to generate positive attitudes from an early age (Grootenboer 2003; Sanmartín et al. 2018). Different authors (Solbes 2011; Aydogan, Bozkurt, and Coskun 2015) indicate that the affective rejection of primary and secondary school students is one of the main causes of their failure in science subjects. Thus, it is essential to take this affective dimension into account in pre-service teachers, as it can lead to teachers feeling competent in teaching science (Jeong et al. 2019).

In this context, gamification is one of the wide range of strategies included and considered active learning (Pho and Dinscore 2015). This instruction methodology relates to games, not play (or playfulness), and it consists of the use of game design elements in non-game contexts, specially, in the educational field, to promote different skills like cooperation or engagement (Deterding et al. 2011). Play is perceived as being beneficial in the promotion and development of imagination, creativity, and spontaneous learning. These same characteristics are often necessary for a student's growth in any educational setting (Jenkins and Mason 2020). It is remarkable that gamification applied to education activities has become very important, playing a relevant role, being appreciated for the generality of users, and contributing to positively influence them to use gamified applications (Pho and Dinscore 2015; Rodrigues, Oliveira, and Rodrigues 2019).

The use of games and gamifying strategies in the classroom can increase student satisfaction, grades, collaboration, and motivation to learn. Here, the creation of educational games provides the opportunity for an interdisciplinary approach, considering the importance to promote a realistic environment for the student (Klisch et al. 2012; Nicholson 2018; Ritzhaupt et al. 2021). Many efforts have been made to use games to encourage the construction of scientific knowledge. This type of learning helps to enhance working memory, which is driven by motivation and meaningful engagement and is the locus of assimilation of new material (Clark et al. 2010; Jenkins and Mason 2020). Various authors have shown successful practices using gamification in university teaching, and even reveal that the students who participate tend to achieve better academic performance, motivation, and positive emotions (Su 2019; Yllana-Prieto, Jeong, and González-Gómez 2021b). Also, there are research indicating these benefits as applied in primary education (Halloluwa et al. 2018; Widodo and Rahayu 2019).

Gamification using an Escape Room methodology is still in its early stages in formal educational settings, although there are various studies (Brown, Darby, and Coronel 2019; Sánchez-Martín et al. 2020; Taraldsen et al. 2020) highlighting the successful application of the Escape Room as a didactic tool in university teaching. In this context, by using gamification techniques, students solve problems for themselves by carrying out 'missions' that require them to apply reason, sensation, and then reflection (Jenkins and Mason 2020). Escape rooms are games in which participants solve puzzles, riddles or challenges and use strategies and instructions to escape from the room in time (Nicholson 2018; David et al. 2019). According to some authors (Nicholson 2018; Sánchez-Martín et al. 2020; Yllana-Prieto, Jeong, and González-Gómez 2021a), it is essential to connect the challenges to the story and background of the escape game, thus attractive students in the narrative. This aspect can help students develop intrinsic incentive to learn and explore further rather than exclusively looking for extrinsic incentive for grades.

Educational Escape Room used to combine other game-based tools such as educational Breakout (Walsh and Spence 2018; Jiménez et al. 2020; Ouariachi and Wim 2020). Breakout is a similar Escape

Room-style game, but rather than the escape of a room, participants are tasked with unlocking a box by using clues and solving puzzles (O'Brien and Pitera 2019; Queiruga-Dios et al. 2020). Numerous studies (Kinio et al. 2019; O'Brien and Pitera 2019; Yllana-Prieto, Jeong, and González-Gómez 2021a) have shown that educational Escape Room and Breakout can improve grade point averages and understanding of concepts. Also, Escape Rooms and Breakout use as didactic tools can increase positive student perception of learning material and decrease course drop-out rates compared to students taught with traditional learning. Other authors (Brown, Darby, and Coronel 2019; Sánchez-Martín et al. 2020; Taraldsen et al. 2020) demonstrate that Escape Room games promotes collaborative work, motivation, and interest of the students. Furthermore, there has been an increase in the number of studies on educational Escape Room and Breakout in recent years, which shows the increasing curiosity concerning these didactic tools in the education research environment (Taraldsen et al. 2020). In this context, there are multiple benefits like students' higher motivation, perceptions, or grades, of the correct use of Escape Room and Breakout as a didactic resource for teaching different STEM contents in primary education (Lathwesen and Belova 2021). According to Hunt-Gómez et al. (2020), the educational Escape Room is considered an excellent educational resource as well as an adequate alternative teaching methodology that pre-service teachers can apply later in their primary school classrooms.

The main objective of this study is to design and describe a tool which combine an Escape Room and Breakout game. We called this instrument 'BrEscapeRm', and it is used as an educational tool to review STEM contents taught in a theoretical class of a science course at the Primary Education degree of the University of Extremadura (Spain).

Materials and methods

Course context and sample

A BrEscapeRm has been carried out on content about the Universe for pre-service teachers enrolled in the course 'Teaching of Matter and Energy' of degree in Primary Education at University of Extremadura (Spain). This course has a total of 150 hours (6 credits).

According to the course syllabus, the 'Teaching of Matter and Energy' framework is to teach and learn science in primary education in general, and specifically teaching about the Universe, the matter and its transformation and the energy. Also, the students must learn how to apply different methodologies to teach scientific contents to primary education students. Specifically, the proposed BrEscapeRm has been designed to review the contents of the Universe lesson. This lesson includes contents related to the size of the Universe, the Universe fundamental structures and bodies, the Solar System and design of activities for the primary school classroom.

The sample consisted of a total of 66 students divided into three groups. Due to the size of the laboratory and capacity restrictions due to COVID-19, the activity was carried out in each laboratory session with 22 students. In the laboratory, students were distributed in pairs and placed at each workstation, which is properly indicated. During the BrEscapeRm, participants must have their mobile phones to scan QR codes and look up information, when necessary, a scientific calculator and they can consult the theory notes if required. The instructors had an active role and constant attention to the participants doubts helping the interaction of participants through the session. During the proposed activity, all recommended safety protocols and health measures have been applied.

Brescaperm description

The implementation has been proposed as a review activity due to the contents included in the BrEscapeRm are explained in the previous theoretical class sessions. Table 1 shows the specific contents

Table 1. Contents worked during tasks and challenges of the BrEscapeRm.

CONTENT	TASK/CHALLENGE
Eclipses. Differences between lunar eclipse and solar eclipse. Positions of the celestial bodies.	Task 1
Solar System planets. Order, composition, relative size, and satellites.	Challenge A
Perimeter. Relation between diameter and radius and how it is calculated.	Task 2
Minerals. Recognition, importance, and differentiation of some of them (talc, gypsum, calcite, fluorite, apatite, orthoclase, quartz, topaz, corundum).	Challenge B
Seasons. Relation, influencing factors and position of the Earth relative to the Sun.	Task 3
Tides. Forces of attraction of the Moon and the Sun and their effect on the Earth.	
Eclipses. Influencing factors, differences between solar, lunar, partial and total. Differences between lunar and terrestrial orbit.	
General Solar System concepts: dwarf planet, equinox, asteroid, galaxy, precession, nutation, comet, star, planet, satellite, nebula.	Task 4
Density. What it depends on and how it is calculated.	
Weight and mass. Differences, calculation, and dependence of each magnitude. Difference between Kg and Newton.	Task 5
PH. Measurement, usefulness, concept, and value of some everyday substances, use of litmus paper (pH-sensitive paper).	Challenge C
Understanding of the order and relative size of the celestial bodies in the Solar System.	
Layout and construction skills.	Task 6
General mathematical calculation, use of the scientific calculator, operations with scientific notation.	
QR code scanning.	Throughout the tasks
Collaborative teamwork. Consensual decision-making, deductive thinking.	

that have been included in the BrEscapeRm and it shows in which the stage of the proposed activity they have been worked.

The BrEscapeRm designed was developed through 6 tasks that follow a sequential model (Nicholson 2015), that is, students had to solve each test in a specific order to be able to move on to the next one. Some tasks contain various challenges, some tasks lead to clues and some tasks reveal padlock codes or keys. Sometimes participants were interacted with the instructor to validate a task or challenge (see Figure 1).

To evaluate the BrEscapeRm designed as a didactic tool, a 3-item questionnaire has been used to gauge how the students perceived the activity as whole, its tasks and challenges. Precisely, participants were asked to rate the tasks, and to provide feedback for improving them (see Table 2). The questionnaire was applied after intervention.

Brescaperm design

An BrEscapeRm has been designed and used as an educational tool to teach STEM contents to pre-service teachers. This BrEscapeRm has been implemented as a review activity of the theoretical contents previously taught in theory classes of the subject 'Didactics of Matter and Energy' of the bilingual degree in Primary Education at University of Extremadura (Spain).

The first 10 minutes were dedicated to explaining what an 'Escape Room' and a 'Breakout' are for students who were not familiar with these terms. In addition, the terms 'gamification' and 'active learning' were explained. Various rules and tips were also specified to confrontation the BrEscapeRm correctly.

As it is an activity that works on the content of the Universe, everything is contextualised around the famous astrophysicist Stephen Hawking. At each workstation, each pair found a big box closed

Table 2 . Questionnaire used to obtain the students' perceptions towards the BrEscapeRm.

QUESTION	DESCRIPTION
Q1	Which task or challenge did you like the most? Why?
Q2	Which task or challenge did you like the least? Why?
Q3	What would you change about the BrEscapeRm you have done?

Figure 1. General flowchart of the BrEscapeRm.

by a 4-digit padlock, a 60 × 40 cm cork sheet cover with paper on the surface and half a big polystyrene ball, a letter, and a rack with five test tubes and five pH sensitive-papers (Figure 2). The letter contains a message from Stephen Hawking in which he is angry about the lack of knowledge and interest of today's young people in the Universe, so he has locked them in the laboratory, and

Figure 2. Workstation. It contains a big box closed by a 4-digit padlock, a cork sheet, half a big polystyrene ball, a letter, and a rack with five test tubes and five pH sensitive-papers.

Figure 3. Boxes and padlocks used in the BrEscapeRm.

they must solve a series of riddles so that their assistants, the instructors, will give them the key to escape from the room.

There is a total of three boxes locked by padlocks in the BrEscapeRm. Box 1 is the biggest box and contains a medium-sized box (Box 2). This box contains Box 3, which is the smallest box. Box 1 is locked by a 4-digit padlock, Box 2 is locked by a key padlock and Box 3 is locked by a 3-digit padlock (Figure 3).

Task 1: puzzle

The letter on the workstation is itself a task. It contains a QR code that redirects to a virtual puzzle that the students must solve by scanning it. After having solved this puzzle, the students were able to read 'To get the second task you must tell the instructor in which position the Moon, Earth and Sun are when there is a lunar eclipse'. When the pair told the instructor the correct answer, the instructor gave them the next task (Figure 4).

Task 2: Solar System components

The second task consists of a double challenge. In the first challenge (Challenge A), students had to fill in a table with information about the planets of the Solar System to obtain a combination. In the second challenge (Challenge B) participants had to identify a specific mineral and obtain a number. Regarding the Challenge A (Figure 5), students had to fill in the table with information about the order, composition (solid or gaseous), presence of satellites and perimeter of each planet in the Solar System. This could be done with the help of internet bibliography and class notes. To obtain the perimeter of each planet, students had to calculate it from the planet diameters. Some letters and numbers in the table are underlined in red. When they filled in the table correctly and replaced the gaps with the words and numbers in red, the sentence below revealed a three-digit number. This number is the first three digits that open the padlock in the Box 1.

The Challenge B (Figure 6) is a description of a unknow mineral. This statement is backwards, so students had to start reading it from right to left and from bottom to top in order to find out what it says. The statement defines the mineral quartz. Once they knew the answer, the participants had to

Hello,

I am Stephen Hawking, but you can call me Don Stephen.

Yes, for those of you who think I have been dead for 3 years, that is a lie. I am enjoying my well-deserved holiday on an island paradise in Oceania (I will not tell you which one), I was fed up with fame and I had to fake my death so that the media would leave me alone. But I always enjoyed what I did, and I am proud to have taught the world so much.

In case you did not know, I am a theoretical physicist, astrophysicist, cosmologist, and science communicator. Among other things, I am well known for my study and theory of black holes.

But I have had enough of this society's lack of knowledge about the Universe around them, even if it is only the basics. That is why I have hired these professors to lock you in this room and not let you out until you have completed a series of tests personally prepared by me, don't you feel lucky?

To win, you must complete a model of the Solar System. Simple, isn't it? For a bit of fun, I have hidden the necessary materials for you. Follow the instructions if you want to get out...

Here is the first task, it is time to use your phone for more than just looking at Instagram.

Good luck...

S. Hawking
Stephen Hawking

To get the second task you must tell the instructor in which position the Moon, Earth and Sun are when there is a lunar eclipse

TASK 1

⏪ RESET
🔗 COMPARTIR ENLACE

Figure 4. Task 1: Letter with QR (Quick Response) code that redirects to the puzzle.

choose among 9 minerals numbered from 1 to 9. Only if the chosen mineral was correct, the students got the fourth number of the combination that opens Box 1.

Task 3: earth interactions videos

After opening Box 1, participants found a medium-sized box (Box 2) locked by a Key padlock and the Task 3. This task consists of six QR codes paired two by two. Each code on the left side redirects to a short video about a specific content related to the interactions of the Earth with the Sun and the Moon. Specifically, the contents worked on with these videos are the Moon-Earth attraction, the seasons and eclipses. The QR codes on the right-hand side lead to a digital padlock, each with a question about its respective video. Each digital padlock provides parts of a link that lead to an audio

PLANET	Perimeter (without decimals)	Order	Solid/Gaseous	Satellites (yes/not)
Mercurio	__ mil km	-----	-----	---
Júpiter	__ mil km	-----	-----	YES
Marte	__ mil km	-----	-----	---
Tierra	__ mil km	-----	SOLID	---
Venus	__ mil km	-----	-----	---
Neptuno	__ mil km	EIGHTH	-----	---
Saturno	__ mil km	-----	-----	---
Urano	__ mil km	-----	-----	---

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Figure 5. Challenge A of the Task 2: Table of planets.

Figure 6. Challenge B of the Task 2: Minerals.

message. In the audio students could hear Stephen Hawking’s voice saying, ‘The key is under the table’. Each pair was able to discover that the key that opens Box 2 was hidden under the table at each workstation (Figure 7).

Task 4: crossword

Inside Box 2, participants found Task 4 and Box 3 closed by a 3-digit padlock. Task 4 consists of a crossword puzzle on general contents about the Solar System and a ‘QR maze’ with numerous QR codes (Figure 8). Some of the letters in the crossword puzzle are marked with red and blue colours. By arranging the letters of each colour in a logical order, the words ‘five’ and ‘four’ can

Figure 7. Task 3 and the Box 2 key.

Figure 8. Task 4, crossword about Solar System concepts and 'QR maze'.

be formed, and if each word is placed where indicated it can read 'Row five, Column four'. These are the references the students took to select the only valid QR code, which could read 'For the instructor to give you the next test you have to tell him the word 5 in the crossword'. This word was 'Nutation', when the instructor received this password and checked that the crossword is correctly solved, instructor gave them Task 5.

Task 5: density, weight, mass, and pH

Task 5 contains a triple challenge. Students worked on the average density of some planets by solving Challenge A. Challenge B contains concepts of weight and mass on the different planets. Students worked on the concept of pH in Challenge C.

Challenge A (Figure 9) consists of a table with the volume and mass of the planets Earth, Mars, Saturn, and Uranus. Students calculated the average density of each planet from this data. This challenge provides the first digit of the 3-digit padlock.

In Challenge B (Figure 10) a problem is proposed. The statement asks about the weight on other planets of a person who weighs 70 kilograms on Earth. To solve this problem, some data are provided, such as the gravity of each planet, the fact that 70 kg on Earth is about 686 Newton and the equivalence between kilograms and Newton. With this challenge, the second number of the 3-digit padlock is obtained.

In Challenge C (Figure 11), basic conceptions of pH have been worked on. The participants had five test tubes with substances and five pieces of pH-sensitive paper on each workstation. The students had to measure the pH of each substance with the pH-sensitive paper and compare the colours with the caption previously uploaded on the virtual platform of the course. In the sheet there are images of the substances tested and some mathematical symbols. As each substance is equivalent to the number of its pH, each number must be substituted in each image and, finally, solve the operation and obtain a single-digit number. Participants found next to the challenge a

A

	Earth	Mars	Saturn	Uranus
VOLUME:	$1,083 \times 10^{12} \text{ km}^3$	$1,6318 \times 10^{11} \text{ km}^3$	$8,27 \times 10^{14} \text{ km}^3$	$6,834 \times 10^{13} \text{ km}^3$
MASS:	$5,972 \times 10^{24} \text{ kg}$	$6,39 \times 10^{23} \text{ kg}$	$5,683 \times 10^{26} \text{ kg}$	$8,681 \times 10^{25} \text{ kg}$
AVERAGE DENSITY:				

*First, round to 4 decimals. Adding only the coefficient of the densities will give you a number with 2 entire numbers and 4 decimals. Take the last decimal.

Figure 9. Challenge A of Task 5. Calculate the average density of planets Earth, Mars, Saturn, and Uranus.

picture of a padlock with the letters A, B, and C written in the combination (Figure 11). If they replaced each letter with the number obtained in each challenge, the 3-digit padlock of Box 3 was opened.

Task 6: Solar System model

When the participants opened Box 3, they found some materials (8 pins, 4 small polystyrene balls, 2 medium balls, 2 big balls and small stones) and an instruction indicating the final task (Task 6) they were to perform. This task consisted of building a model of the Solar System with the materials they have found in this box and the one they already had on the workstation (cork sheet and the half big polystyrene ball) (Figure 12).

Once the pair of students thought they had the model built correctly they call the instructor, and he/she would decide if it was right or wrong. If it was right, the instructor would give the couple the key to the laboratory and a badge certifying that they have successfully completed the BrEscapeRm.

B My mass is 70kg on Earth (686 Newton). But is my weight the same on other planets? I will give you the gravity of each planet to make the calculation:

	<u>Gravity</u>	<u>Newton</u>	<u>Weights (Kg) [Round to 3 decimals]</u>
Mercury:	3,70 m/s ²		
Venus:	8,87 m/s ²		
Mars:	3,71 m/s ²		
Jupiter:	24,79 m/s ²		
Saturn:	10,44 m/s ²		
Uranus:	8,87 m/s ²		
Neptune:	11,15 m/s		

1N = 0,102 kg

*Add the rounded weights and take the last decimal number.

Figure 10. Challenge B of Task 5. Calculate the weight of a person on other planets

Figure 11. Challenge C of Task 5 (pH test) and padlock clue.

Results

Analysis of students' perceptions

Students' perceptions about the implemented BrEscapeRm have been evaluated by the questionnaire that was applied after the BrEscapeRm. The first question deals with the tasks and challenges that they liked the most and the reasons (Figure 13). Here, the two tasks that were more frequently mentioned by the students were the challenge C of task 5 (pH test) with 26 mentions and task 6 (Solar System model) with 21 mentions. These two tasks were highly rated by students because they find them to be funny, instructive, dynamic, and interesting.

The second question is about the tasks and challenges that were least liked and the reasons (Figure 14). In this case, the challenges A (Density of planets) and B (Weight problem) of task 5 must be highlighted for gathering a high number of mentions (37). Task 1 (Puzzle) was the second less rated task (11 mentions), and challenge C (pH test) of task 5 the third less rated (5 mentions). The most frequent reasons given by students to justify these answers were the presence of

Figure 12. Students making a model of the solar system.

Figure 13. Most rated tasks during the BrEscapeRm development.

many mathematical calculations, high degree of difficulty, long tasks, and the need of much more student autonomy.

The third question asks about several general aspects that could be improved and suggestions on how to improve them (Figure 15). At this point, most of the students (44 of 66) indicated that they would not change anything overall as they were satisfied with BrEscapeRm. However, some students proposed different interesting improvements. Here, students repeated aspects such as the improvement of the application used to do the puzzle in task 1, eliminating the competitive factor between groups, shorter general duration, use of more space in the lab to move around more, and groups of more members.

Discussion

An implementation and development of the BrEscapeRm designed has been described. After that, there are some aspects that it is important to point out. In the bibliographical review, we found that there are numerous studies that show the benefits of the educational Escape Room and Break-out in the context of active learning methodologies and gamification (Kinio et al. 2019; Watermeier and Salzameda 2019; Veldkamp et al. 2020). The educational Escape Room – Breakout, such as

Figure 14. Less rated tasks during the BrEscapeRm development.

BrEscapeRm, has important advantages such as the generation of positive emotions and motivation and it could even improve the primary students' meaningful learning of some theoretical concepts. According to the results obtained after the BrEscapeRm, it was noted that some of the reasons for liking certain tasks were that students found them funny, interesting, motivating, or exciting. This generation of positive emotions and positive attitudes is very useful and important, especially in pre-service teachers, due to most students are Humanities and Social Sciences background. This background could be implicated that these students tend to have negative emotions and bad experiences towards STEM contents (González-Gómez, Jeong, and Gallego-Picó 2018; Yllana-Prieto, Jeong, and González-Gómez 2021a). In this sense, the sample of this research was composed of pre-service teachers with a Humanities and Social Sciences educational background. This educational background could explain the participants' rejection of some aspects of science such as calculations and formulas. Here, it has been observed that some of the reasons why students disliked certain tasks were the calculations, the high difficulty, and some negative emotions such as impatience and nervousness.

It is important to consider the control of some variables during the development of an Escape Room and Breakout activity. The time taken by each student to solve the tasks and the total time

Improve aspects

Figure 15. Students' suggestions for improvement about the BrEscapeRm in general.

taken to solve the BrEscapeRm is different, and it is a variable to be considered (Contreras and Eguía 2017; Yllana-Prieto, Jeong, and González-Gómez 2021a). The difficulty of the activity and the level of knowledge of each student make it an additional difficulty for the instructor. Therefore, it is important to design the activities carefully according to the level of the students and to obtain a balance between the difficulty of the challenges and the time it takes to solve them. It is essential that the role of the instructor must be active, especially in educational Escape Rooms and Breakout in the context of active learning, as he/she must be always considerate to help and resolve any questions that may arise during the activity (Nicholson 2015; Sierra and Fernández-Sánchez 2019).

The BrEscapeRm proposed was finished within the expected time, which shows that the general difficulty was correct, and it was neither too easy nor too difficult. Although students pointed out that the presence of calculations and problems were the main reasons for dissatisfaction, these contents are in the syllabus of the subject and were fully adapted to the level required in the course. During BrEscapeRm development, it could see that the students were very focused on each task and there was a sense of pleasure at the end of BrEscapeRm. Here, several of the most repeated reasons given by the participants were that the tasks were funny, didactic, dynamic, interesting, and motivating.

In order to improve the BrEscapeRm in the following years, students were asked to propose some general feedback. 67% of participants (44 students) did not propose any, as they were completely satisfied with the overall development of the designed BrEscapeRm. Many of these students reported that the difficulty and duration of the BrEscapeRm were correct. However, the rest of the students proposed the improvement of different technical facets of the BrEscapeRm. Various of these suggestions were to reduce the competitiveness, to use more spaces in the lab to move around, shorter tasks, or to improve the applications for puzzles and QR codes.

Conclusions

According to the BrEscapeRm development, the different tasks and challenges appear to be of adequate difficulty due to the BrEscapeRm has been completed within the estimated time. During the BrEscapeRm there is an atmosphere of satisfaction and concentration on the part of the participants. Here, the students pointed out that the developed BrEscapeRm was funny, interesting, motivating, and exciting. This environment could help students to take a greater interest in the STEM courses. As

it was reported before, this is especially important in pre-service teachers, due to most of them have Humanities and Social Sciences background, and they might have less interest towards STEM courses. Thus, it is essential to provide pre-service teachers with new methodologies and tools that can foster a good environment for teaching STEM content with their future primary school students. In this sense, a certain rejection of the use of calculation and difficulty of science contents by the students was observed. The transversal nature of the BrEscapeRm design makes this activity ideal for reviewing most of the content about the Universe taught in theoretical classes but also helps to review some basic mathematical concepts such as density, weight, mass, perimeter, and basic calculation. However, during the activity it is essential that the role of the instructor was always active and that the tasks were connected to the story and background of the intervention. Although this research is a preliminary study, the results presented, are promising for future research. The BrEscapeRm designed could have multiple benefits in the primary student's motivation and engagement. However, it still needs to be improved with some of the proposals that students have suggested to make learning more effective (less competitiveness, using more laboratory spaces, shorter tasks, and improving the applications). The BrEscapeRm designed seems to be a useful educational tool to teach STEM contents of pre-service teachers, and therefore, can be a successful way for teaching this type of contents in primary education.

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